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Asian Language Teaching and Learning – The Influence of Technology on Students' Skills in SL Classroom

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Outline

1. Mobile learning and language teaching
2. Introduction of MemAsia project
 1. Motivation and objectives
 2. Preliminary research
 3. Construction of materials
 4. Presentation of software
 5. Results
3. Commentary and conclusions

Introduction of MemAsia project

- **Asian** language education and technology
- Supported by **EU** social funds 2015/2016
- Three researchers, 4 languages
 - Japanese
 - Korean
 - Hindi
 - Sanskrit
- Introduction of **memory algorithms** to classroom study

Asian languages in Croatia: motivation for this project

- To find out more about Croatian learners of four target languages
 - Difficulties in learning
 - How to enhance results
 - The role of technology
- To provide a basis for construction of systematic study materials
- Long-term: to provide an e-environment for Asian languages study
 - Include in the classrooms of Croatia
 - Share all materials online for (inter)national use

Preliminary research: attitudes

- Attitudes about mobile and traditional learning

MEMAZIJA

ALGORITMI ZA PAMĆENJE I NJIHOVA PRIMJENA U
UČENJU AZIJSKIH JEZIKA

Experience prior to MemAsia

- **over 60%** of students engage with their mobile devices at least 3-4 times an hour
- only **48 out of 203** students had had a chance to engage with e-tools in their language classrooms
 - mostly students of Japanese language
- Majority have **at least once** used one of the following:
 - Duolingo, Memrise, Quizlet, Anki, Lang8, WaniKani. Resources such as Busuu, Cram, Pleco, Lingvist.io, FluentU
- Students inclined to try e-learning more
- **Memrise, Quizlet and Anki** chosen as a basis for Croatian materials

Construction of e-learning and mobile learning materials

- Goal: produce systematic materials to follow classroom curriculum for Japanese, Korean Hindi and Sanskrit
 - **All** vocabulary and grammar from textbooks
 - Divided in **levels** and standardized
 - Translated to **Croatian** (not English)
 - Accessible from any **computer or smartphone**
 - Students in need provided with phones
 - Implemented in **different courses**

Examples

- Materials can be used on both desktop and mobile platforms
- Most students use the **mobile** versions
- Note:

Applications developed by various external developers

Materials developed by MemAsia

- Presenting the examples of mobile version of applications

Example 1: Memrise

Three course cards are shown, each with a 'MEMAZIJA' logo and a 'CONTINUE' button. The top card is for Japanese A1: Vokabular (Level 0/56, 229,807 points). The middle card is for Hindi A1: Gramatika i rečenice (Level 8/50, 229,807 points). The bottom card is for Sanskrit A2.2: Gramatika (Level 3/11, 229,807 points).

The mobile app home screen shows a central menu with a green hand icon and a blue hand icon. Below the menu are two circular buttons: a blue one labeled 'Classic Review' and a red one labeled 'Speed Review'. The background is a dark blue gradient with a faint 'MEMAZIJA' logo.

The desktop website interface features a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Courses', and 'Groups'. The main content area is titled 'Japanese' and lists several courses: 'Memazija Japanski A1: Rečenice i gramatika' (10 / 134 words learned), 'Memazija Japanski A1: Vokabular' (10 / 768 words learned), 'Memazija Japanski A2: Rečenice i gramatika' (0 / 180 words learned), and 'Memazija Japanski A2: Vokabular' (7 / 751 words learned). A 'Streak Clock' shows 2 hours and 35 minutes left. A 'PRO' section offers a monthly subscription for \$9. A 'Leaderboard' shows the top 4 users: smellyeye (13,050), kendoka_v (6,446), Shin314 (5,319), and Rhivi (4,528).

Example 1: Memrise

Ready to learn Ready to review Ignore

おはよう (ございます)	dobro jutro	
こんにちは	dobar dan	
こんばんは	dobra večer	
さようなら	doviđenja	
おやすみ (なさい)	laku noć	
ありがとう (ございます)	hvala	
すみません	oprostite; ispričavam se	

いいえ

さようなら

Select the correct **Croatian** for the **Japanese** above:

1. hvala 2. dobra večer

3. doviđenja 4. knjižnica

See answer

Learn 5 new wo...

doobar dan

Type the Japanese for the Croatian above and press Enter:

こんにちは

See answer

こんにちは こんにちは! 今日は コンニチハ

q w e r t y u i o p

@ # \$ % & * + ()

↑ z x c v b n m ←

?123 日本語 実行

Example 1: Memrise

Japanese 1 90

arigatou
thank you

1/3 MEMS

Japanese 1 180

Type the Japanese for the English

hello

Input field with a vertical cursor

Learn new words

RESULTS LEADERBOARD WORDS (3)

Your Results

- 3 words learned
- 75% accuracy
- 466 points earned

Daily goal

466 / 10

SET A DAILY GOAL

T W T F S S M

HOME CONTINUE

Example 2: Quizlet

전공	studij (major)	🔊	★
컴퓨터 그래픽	računalna grafika	🔊	★
경제학	ekonomija	🔊	★
한국어 교육	podučavanje korejskog jezika	🔊	★

Example 2: Quizlet

Example 3: Anki

AnkiDroid
7667개의 카드 예정 (58 min)

- Default 0 0 100
- JLPT N1 Vocab 20 3 7
- > JPNS 20 0 21
- ▼ Japanese 20 0 1
 - Study Group 20 0 1
 - Memazija-Hangeul 18 1 3
 - Memazija-Kanji 0.4 20 13 18
 - Nihongo So-Matome N1 Grammar 20 3 50
 - Ultimate Geography 10 0 156
 - 完全マスター 1級文法問題 対策例文 20 10 10
 - 맞춤 학습 세션 27

Studied 0 cards in 0 minutes today

Memazija-Hangeul
1분 남음

18 1 3

čamac

< 1 min 다시 (red)

1 d 관참음 (green)

4 d 쉬음 (blue)

Memazija-Hangeul
1분 남음

18 0 2

đurđica

< 1 min 다시 (red)

< 10 min 관참음 (green)

4 d 쉬음 (blue)

Example 3: Anki

snaga
리키, 리ョク, ちから
toliko sam SNAŽAN da mogu podići
katanu

rezati
사이, 세ツ, き · ー
sedam katana koje REŽU

žlica / čovjek koji sjedi
ヒ, さじ
žlica slična "hi" u katakani, hito =
čovjek

Example 3: Anki

Ultimate Geography 통계

복습 횟수 복습 시간 간격 시간별 분석 주간 분석

Ultimate Geography 통계

간격 시간별 분석 주간 분석 답변 버튼 카드 형식

스크린샷 저장 중...

Ultimate Geography 통계

간격 시간별 분석 주간 분석 답변 버튼 카드 형식

Results (so far)

- Students of all four languages
 - Tested every 2-3 months
 - Standardized tests on a computer
 - Measuring results and comparing with usage
- Results from **regular** users and **occasional** users significantly different
- Regular users show **~20% improvement** in test results on each testing

Additional applications

- Data from the apps can be used for various research on **memory and study issues**
- Collected and stored for future work and reference
- Insight about human memory, learning and importance of **algorithms** for spaced repetition

Conclusions, comments...

- **Most important elements** in successful implementation of mobile and e-learning in classrooms
 - **Systematic** and wholesome materials which **follow classwork**
 - **Motivation**
 - Promotion of usage by teachers (weekly quizzies)
 - Tracking and measuring progress
 - **Fun** : charts and games

Conclusions, comments...

- **Other** important elements in successful implementation of mobile and e-learning in classrooms
 - Smart **algorithm** for repetition
 - Availability and **stability** of applications
 - **Ease** of usage
 - Both for construction of materials and usage by students

Thank you for your attention!

Thank You